

Response to Jan Slowak’s critique of “Einstein’s Cat: A Thought Experiment on the Universality of Time Dilation”

V.G. Rousseau¹

¹*Physics Department, Xavier University of Louisiana, 1 Drexel Dr., New Orleans, LA 70125, USA*

This note is a response to Jan Slowak’s critique[1] of the peer-reviewed paper Einstein’s Cat: A Thought Experiment on the Universality of Time Dilation[2, 3]. Slowak presents his critique as a logical analysis grounded in his “understanding” of Special Relativity. Although it is difficult to elaborate on the properties of the empty set, we show that his claimed understanding fails to engage with either the mathematical structure or the empirical foundations of the theory. No explicit alternative framework is formulated, no quantitative predictions are derived, and no experimental inconsistencies are demonstrated. Instead, his purported “counterarguments” consist primarily of restating the leitmotif that he wishes Einstein’s Relativity were wrong, while failing to identify a single inconsistency in the theory and — above all — without addressing the fact that Special Relativity has been continuously validated experimentally for over 120 years, including in everyday technological systems whose operation depends quantitatively on its predictions.

INTRODUCTION

The hardest thing to understand in the Theory of Relativity is why so many people want to believe it is wrong. One of the most criticized results of Einstein’s Relativity is the time dilation effect. While many deniers naively believe that time dilation is merely an optical effect arising from light travel time, others acknowledge that the effect is more profound but fail to understand that it reflects how the Universe actually behaves. Concluding that it “makes no sense”, they infer that it must therefore be *wrong*. This is a good place to recall Neil deGrasse Tyson’s famous quote: “*The Universe is under no obligation to make sense to you*”[4].

It is a curious fact that, just like flat-earthers, anti-relativists are found all over the globe, making their way to community meetings guided by relativity-corrected GPS. Faced with overwhelming evidence [5, 6], some at least acknowledge the reality of time dilation, but they won’t give up on their dream of Einstein being *wrong*, so they attempt to confine it to light-based clocks. In particular, they claim that time dilation does not apply to mechanical or biological systems (e.g. human cells)[7–9].

It is as a response to these claims that the thought experiment “*Einstein’s Cat*” which introduces the *Sync-Or-Die clock* was proposed[2, 3], to which the anti-relativist Jan Slowak replied with his critique[1]. While most anti-relativists lack scientific training (which explains their difficulties with the theory), Slowak distinguishes himself by claiming a background in mathematics and computer science. This claim stands in stark contradiction with his critique, which reveals an inability to engage in even elementary abstract reasoning. In particular, dismissing a thought experiment as disconnected from reality is no more defensible than dismissing the Pythagorean theo-

rem because perfect right triangles do not exist.¹

I shall now address Slowak’s flawed points.

RESPONSE TO SLOWAK’S POINT 1: ALLEGED CIRCULAR REASONING

The claim that my argument is circular is incorrect, and emphasizes Slowak’s inability to understand the article he’s trying to criticize. The universality of time dilation is not assumed in my paper, it is derived! The starting assumption is that time dilation applies to light clocks, as it follows from Einstein’s postulates, and as it is accepted by anti-relativists in references[7–9]. The Sync-Or-Die clock does not assume universality, instead it illustrates the physical consequences of abandoning Lorentz invariance while retaining frame-independent outcomes.

Calling this “circular” is equivalent to calling the Pythagorean theorem circular because it follows from Euclidean axioms, which is simply absurd.

RESPONSE TO SLOWAK’S POINT 2: DEFINITION OF THE PARADOX

The critique treats frame-independent physical outcomes as an optional feature of Special Relativity, whereas it is in fact a minimal requirement for any coherent physical theory. Abandoning this requirement does not resolve the paradox, it removes the possibility of defining a consistent physical outcome altogether.

If the cat is dead, it is dead, not “dead in one frame and alive in another”. This is not a relativity issue, it is

¹ It is outrageous that such a pseudo-scientist is allowed to sell on Amazon a book full of misinformation for \$29.50, shamelessly exploiting unaware people’s gullibility[10]. I invite the people who got scammed to request a refund.

a consistency-of-reality issue. If observers cannot agree on the outcome, the theory does not describe physics. It merely reflects the failure to describe a single consistent reality.

RESPONSE TO SLOWAK'S POINT 3: PHYSICAL FEASIBILITY OF THE EXPERIMENT

The criticism that the Sync-or-Die clock is not physically realizable misunderstands the purpose of a thought experiment.

Thought experiments are used to expose logical consequences, not to propose laboratory apparatuses. Schrödinger's cat, Maxwell's demon, and Einstein's elevator are not engineering blueprints, and neither is the Sync-or-Die clock. It is designed to test logical consistency. Whether such a device could be constructed with springs and mirrors is entirely irrelevant.

It is amazing that someone who supposedly studied mathematics is capable of making such a critique. If we followed his reasoning, we would conclude that the Pythagorean theorem has no connection with reality because perfect right triangles don't exist.

RESPONSE TO SLOWAK'S POINT 4: MEASUREMENT UNCERTAINTY AND ITS IMPLICATIONS

Measurement uncertainty affects experimental precision, not theoretical structure.

The argument in my paper does not rely on resolving infinitesimal differences between clocks in practice. It concerns whether frame-invariant physical outcomes are possible if time dilation were not universal. Introducing real-world noise does not resolve logical contradictions. By the same reasoning, one could dismiss conservation laws because measurements are imperfect. Again, the Pythagorean theorem would have to be discarded because no triangle can be measured with perfect precision.

RESPONSE TO SLOWAK'S POINT 5: ALTERNATIVE INTERPRETATION

The appeal to unspecified "alternative frameworks" in which clocks behave differently is not an argument against Special Relativity.

Physics is not refuted by proposing logical possibilities, it is challenged by empirically viable alternatives. Any model in which different clocks accumulate different elapsed times along the same worldline must reproduce, at minimum, the results of:

- Muon lifetime experiments

- Relativistic corrections in GPS
- Atomic clock transport experiments
- Particle accelerator timing measurements

No such framework is presented by Slowak, nor is any quantitative prediction offered that matches or improves upon Special Relativity. Without this, the invocation of alternatives remains speculative, unquantified, and non-falsifiable.

RESPONSE TO SLOWACK'S ADDITIONAL REMARKS ON THE VALIDITY OF SPECIAL RELATIVITY

The assertion that Special Relativity is "fundamentally incorrect" is stated but not demonstrated. Citing one's own non-peer-reviewed (and likely peer-rejected) work does not substitute for empirical evidence or predictive success.

Special Relativity is not upheld by consensus or aesthetics, but by its continued experimental verification and technological indispensability. Any claim of its invalidity must account quantitatively for the vast body of data that currently confirms it. For that matter, it is worth emphasizing one of the greatest successes of Quantum Field Theory (which fully incorporates Einstein's Special Relativity), namely the prediction of the value of the anomalous magnetic moment of the electron that matches the experimental value with an agreement to 15 significant figures. Can someone please tell Slowak that the probability of this agreement being accidental is on the order of one in a quadrillion?

RESPONSE TO SLOWAK'S CONCLUDING REMARKS

The reference to "Einstein's Cat" is not rhetorical embellishment but a pedagogical device, explicitly intended for physics education. The article was published in Physics Education, not as a foundational reform proposal. Its aim is clarity, not novelty.

Lastly, the criticism about me calling "Einstein's Cat" a thought experiment that explicitly involves Einstein and his cat Tiger, which supposedly "complicates the argument", testifies to a desperate attempt to knock down an iron monument with a feather.

CONCLUSION

Slowak's critique does not identify a logical inconsistency in the paper, nor does it present an empirically supported alternative framework. Instead, it objects to

conclusions that are mathematically unavoidable once Lorentz invariance is accepted, while simultaneously rejecting that invariance without experimental justification.

Disagreement with Special Relativity is not, by itself, an argument against a pedagogical illustration of its consequences.

-
- [1] Jan Slowak, *Analysis of the article: Einstein's cat: a thought experiment on the universality of time dilation*, ResearchGate, (2025), <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21950.40005>
- [2] Val G. Rousseau, *Einstein's Cat: A Thought Experiment on the Universality of Time Dilation*, V G Rousseau 2025 Phys. Educ. 60 055014 (2025).
- [3] Val G. Rousseau, *Einstein's Cat: The Thought Experiment That Debunks Anti-Relativity Myths!*, YouTube, (2025), <https://youtu.be/nxAPELzc8hc>
- [4] Neil DeGrasse Tyson, *Astrophysics for people in a hurry*. W. W. Norton & Company (2017).
- [5] Hafele, J. C., & Keating, R. E. (1972). *Around-the-World Atomic Clocks: Observed Relativistic Time Gains*. Science, 177(4044), 166–168.
- [6] Nagel, M., Parker, S., Kovalchuk, E. et al. Direct terrestrial test of Lorentz symmetry in electrodynamics to 10–18. Nat Commun 6, 8174 (2015).
- [7] Richard Sauerheber and Edwin Espinoza, *Characteristics of light: Velocity, massless energy, and special relativity*, Optik Volume 168, September 2018, Pages 974-986.
- [8] Joseph Lévy, *Aether Theory Clock Retardation vs. Special Relativity Time Dilation*, arXiv:physics/0611077v5.
- [9] Oleg D. Jefimenko, *Electromagnetic Retardation and Theory of Relativity: New Chapters in the Classical Theory of Fields*, ISBN 9780917406256.
- [10] Jan Slowak, *Special Relativity is nonsense*, Bod - Books on Demand, ISBN-13: 978-9177859659 (2019).